

RULES OF CONTEST

Reference: CONTEST/EFSA/PTT/2016/01

Design of a mobile application prototype

to facilitate general public in accessing
information about EFSA's upcoming, ongoing and
closed work

Table of Contents

1.	OBJECTIVES PURSUED	3
2.	EXPECTED RESULTS	3
3.	ARRANGEMENTS AND DEADLINE FOR THE SUBMISSION OF ENTRIES	3
4.	EVALUATION PROCESS	4
5.	GUIDANCE FOR THE CONTESTANTS	5
6.	AGREEMENT ON OWNERSHIP AND PAYMENT OF THE PRIZE	7
7.	CONDITIONS FOR CANCELLATION OF THE CONTEST, IF ANY	7
8.	CONDITIONS FOR PARTICIPATION	7
9.	OTHER RULES	8

1. OBJECTIVES PURSUED

The contest is a public procurement procedure to acquire a plan or design, to be selected by a jury, after being put out to competition. The overall objective of this contest is to enhance some of [EFSA key values](#) such as openness and innovation in order to enable stakeholders to understand the basis EFSA's scientific work in an innovative manner.

The objective of the present contest is:

To come up with a prototype of a mobile application able to facilitate the general public in obtaining fast and easily understandable information on ongoing or recently closed EFSA work.

2. EXPECTED RESULTS

As a minimum the mobile application should allow the user to:

Minimum requirements

1. Navigate EFSA register of questions database, by allowing performing queries on the various attributes of the EFSA-Question entity.
2. Search for a specific EFSA-Question linked to an evaluation of a certain substance, product or subject (i.e.: aspartame, caffeine, meat, antibiotics, etc...).
3. Allow the users to submit a request for information about the content they have retrieved.
4. Display reports/dashboards on EFSA question status: mandate ongoing, opinion adopted.
5. Arrange the dashboards with different grouping criteria: per unit/panel, per food sector area, per status, per month of adoption.

Other features of interest are

6. Send alerts if the user wishes, on main events about EFSA, such as: new mandate received, new opinion adopted, new public consultation published.
7. Allow the user to configure the alerts they want to receive.
8. Allow the users to submit comments.
9. Other innovative features that the contestants may propose.

See part 5 of these rules for more details.

3. ARRANGEMENTS AND DEADLINE FOR THE SUBMISSION OF ENTRIES

30 June 2016 at 24:00 CET¹

Any economic operator may request clarifications on the present rules of contest by latest 22/06/2016.

Requests for clarification may only be submitted in writing to the following email account:
EFSAProcurement@efsa.europa.eu

The entries, containing detailed written descriptions of the proposed mobile application prototype design, should be submitted via email by the deadline indicated above to the following email account EFSAProcurement@efsa.europa.eu. The application should be in PDF format and be perfectly legible so that there can be no doubt as to the content. Try to stick to maximum 5 pages of description. In addition feel free to attach screen-shots, mock-ups, and wireframes showing the

¹ Central European time

proposed features and / or solutions. In your proposal you can explain how your mobile-app satisfies the below award criteria.

4. EVALUATION PROCESS

The evaluation of written entries will be carried out by the EFSA jury.

Phase 1:

During phase 1, the jury will assess each submitted written solution against the 5 award criteria indicated below with a score range between 0 and 5. The thresholds which must be passed and maximum possible obtainable award scores are indicated in the table below.

Award criteria	Threshold	Weight	Maximum obtainable
1. Impact			
- What is the social impact of the app developed?	2	28%	5
- Can it give more clarity on how EFSA works and on its activities?			
- Does it solve the stated goal of the contest?			
2. Innovation			
- Is the solution novel?	2	26%	5
- Does it solve a problem in a creative or never-seen-before way?			
3. Technical Achievement			
- Is the mobile application completed with the features required and ready to use?	2	15%	5
- Which are the operative systems supported (Android/iOS/Windows)?			
- Does it work on smartphones and tablets?			
4. Easy to Use			
- Is the application user friendly?	2	21%	5
- Is it intuitive?			
- Does it have an attractive design?			
- Are the dashboards animated?			
- Is the application responsive to the user inputs?			
5. Security			
- The contestant should indicate which are the standards adopted to guarantee security and data protection of the users of the application.	2	10%	5
Total	10	100%	25

Phase 2:

The 5 best entries that passed all 5 thresholds may be invited for a 2 day event at EFSA's premises in PARMA which will include:

- 1st day: a demonstration of the mobile app to EFSA Jury of a maximum of 1 hour per team
- 2nd day: announcement of the results and award of the prizes.

Those invited to the 2 day event at EFSA will be paid per person a 400 € lump sum intended to cover the travel and daily substance costs, including the accommodation costs. Up to 4 persons will be reimbursed per entry. More persons can come to the HACKATHON event but with no lump sum granted for them from EFSA.

Finalisation of evaluation:

Following the HACKATHON event, the EFSA Jury will reassess all the demonstrated solutions against the same above award criteria. Upon completion of their evaluation work the EFSA jury shall sign a record of all the entries examined, containing an assessment of their quality and identifying those to which the prizes may be awarded.

Possible prizes

1. The winning application design, following phase 2, will be awarded a prize of 20.000 €.
2. 2nd best solution – 6.000 €
3. 3rd best solution – 3.000 €
4. 4th and 5th best solution – 500 €

Only the entries which pass the minimum quality thresholds described in the above award criteria table will be eligible for a prize.

5. GUIDANCE FOR THE CONTESTANTS

In order to improve your understanding of how EFSA works, and in particular on the Register of Questions, take a look at **Annex 1** – Register of questions user guide.

EFSA is developing software services (WebServices and REST services) that will allow users to retrieve the same information available in the Register of Questions user interfaces. As these services are not yet available, annex 2 has been provided and can be used in order to get an idea of the data that can be retrieved by invoking these software services. The data source used in annex 2 can be retrieved from the Register of Questions by using the “Download” questions feature (see annex 1 for details).

If you read annex 1 you will notice that there is a complex relationship between mandate, question and output, the most general one is that a mandate could generate many questions that could then be joined in one or more outputs:

This relationship is useful when the same mandate generates many questions that are assigned to different EFSA units (departments). For those familiar with project management concepts the mandate could be seen as a program that is split in many different projects that are assigned to a specific unit.

In annex 2 this complex relationship has been flattened, so that when one mandate generates more than one question you will see the same mandate repeated n-times, once for every child question. The same reasoning applies for the outputs i.e. if an output was generated by the

contribution of two questions in the excel table the output will appear twice, once per each question.

The EFSA-questions are very useful in order to understand from an external point of view which activities EFSA is working on during the year, therefore it is possible to find which are the questions on-going, which those that are close to being adopted, or how many questions are there for a certain unit. Currently this information can be retrieved from the Register of Questions database by using the Question Search form. This form allows specifying complex filters on dates, status, unit, food sector area etc... the filters applicable are powerful but they are not of immediate usage. A more user-friendly interface would be needed in order to improve the interaction with the user and to make the search more intuitive. One of the main goals of the mobile application of this contest is in fact to improve the user experience.

Another limit of the current Register of Questions user interface is that it does not allow a visual representation of the data extracted. The feature that allows the download of the list of questions is very useful for those users expert in using excel pivot tables and charts; once downloaded this list can be the data-source for the generation of reports. **Annex 2** is an example of this usage: starting from the downloaded questions a set of charts has been created. The mobile app shall allow the user to generate similar reports in a dynamic and interactive way: for instance the user will be able to filter/drilldown dynamically the dataset using various controls such as combo-box, checklists, radio-lists, etc... or to change the appearance of the report by choosing various types of charts such as histograms, pie charts, bar charts, radar charts, etc... an interesting feature may allow, by clicking on an area of a chart, to retrieve all the related questions. Annex 2 contains the following sheets:

- DataSource: Contains an extraction of all questions visible in the register of questions, and is the source of the data used for the generation of the charts.
- QuestionAdopted2015PerUnit: This pie-chart gives an indication of how many questions have been adopted during 2015 divided per unit.
- ForecastedVsActual: This radar-chart displays per each month of 2015 how many questions have been actually adopted versus those that were forecasted. The chart also tracks the number of new questions received and accepted per month.
- Forecasted2016perQuestionType: This chart gives an indication of the EFSA activities forecasted for 2016 divided per questionType.
- QuestionStatusPerFSA: This chart gives an overall idea of the status of the questions received by EFSA during 2015 and 2016, divided per food-sector-area.

An interesting feature currently available in the EFSA website is the possibility to submit requests to EFSA to get information about how EFSA works in general, or even about a certain question. This form is available at this url: <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/applicationshelpdesk/askaquestion?ScientificArea=zero>

In the mobile app to be developed in this contest, for every question a link to this form could be provided in order to allow the users to insert their requests. A more advanced version would allow insertion of the request directly from the mobile app and foresee/simulate the usage of a web-service to submit the request to EFSA.

One important activity performed by EFSA, is to collect comments from the general public about a scientific opinion/output before its formal publication. This feature is available from the web-site using a form (see for example this consultation: <http://registerofquestions.efsa.europa.eu/roqFrontend/consultation/doc/58> that is now closed). Public Consultations are stored in the register of questions database, and are linked to questions with "questionType" equal to "public consultation", this field together with the question deadline could be used in order to send alerts to the user on upcoming public consultations (deadline - 30days < today date < deadline) and allow the submission of comments on open public consultations (deadline < today data < deadline + 30 days). Such considerations on dates and on question-status could be used to send alerts to the users on relevant events, such as: receipt of a mandate, acceptance of a question, clock stop events, adoption of a question, and publication of an output. An interface could be developed in order to allow the users to register themselves to the main events.

This document and the attached annexes are not meant to be a list of required use-cases to be developed; it is up to the contestants to propose innovative ideas. In **Annex 3** you can find the draft EFSA strategy for the next years. This document contains valuable information in order to

understand our philosophy, and contains the keys for developing the winning mobile app of the Hackathon.

6. AGREEMENT ON OWNERSHIP AND PAYMENT OF THE PRIZE

An agreement will be signed between EFSA and the successful 1st contestant whereby EFSA takes the full ownership of the successful mobile application prototype solution, including any source codes, for which it has paid the 1st prize. The ownership will effectively pass to EFSA only once the prize has been paid to the successful contestant.

For 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th ranked awarded solution, EFSA acquires the right to see the source-code and to implement the solution ideas in another app. The contestants will be allowed to refuse this right to EFSA but such refusal will entail no prize being paid.

In no case will the contestant be allowed to publicize or make available to the public or any third party in any way the mobile application prototype developed under this contest.

All prizes will be paid in one instalment to the bank account indicated by the prize winners within a maximum of 30 days from signature of the draft Ownership Transfer Agreement enclosed in **Annex 4**.

Documents requested:

For EFSA to be able to pay the eventual prize, the contestant shall send, preferably together with the entry, a 1 page Bank Account Form, see link in **Annex 5**. If not sent together with the entry this information will be required from those awarded the prize.

7. CONDITIONS FOR CANCELLATION OF THE CONTEST, IF ANY

EFSA has the right to terminate the contest before its closing date without any obligation to indemnify contestants in case the objective of the contest has been achieved in any other way.

8. CONDITIONS FOR PARTICIPATION

8.1 Eligibility criteria

Participation in this contest is open on equal terms to all natural and legal persons falling within the scope of the EU Treaties. Applicants established in third countries (non-EU countries) do not have the right to participate in contest unless other bilateral or special international agreements in the field of public procurement grant them the right to do so.

When applying the rules of access to the market, it is the country where the applicant is established which should be considered. As regards a natural person, it is the State in which he/she has his/her domicile.

Currently applicants from the following third countries are considered eligible based on signed and ratified international/bilateral agreements in the field of public procurement: FYROM, Albania, Montenegro, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Iceland, Norway and Liechtenstein.

Please note the above list is not exhaustive and is subject to updates. In case of queries regarding eligibility to apply please contact EFSA via above indicated e-mail.

It is possible that a contestant is competing in the contest alone or as a group of persons. In the second case all participating persons must be eligible according to above criteria. One person shall be indicated in the entry as the leading person. If such contestant then wins the 1st prize EFSA will sign the Ownership Transfer Agreement only with the leading person.

Documents requested:

For EFSA to be able to verify the participation eligibility the contestant is required to send together with the entry a 1 page Legal Entity Form, see link in **Annex 5**.

8.2. Exclusion criteria

Contestants which are in one of the situations referred to in Article 106(1) and Article 107 of the EU Financial Regulation are excluded from participating and from award of a prize under the present contest.

Documents requested:

The contestant is required to send together with the entry, a 1 page Declaration on Honour on exclusion criteria, see **Annex 6**, that it/he/she is not in one of those exclusion situations.

9. OTHER RULES

9.1 Sole liability of contestants

EFSA may not be held responsible for any claim relating to the activities carried out in the framework of the contest by the contestant. EFSA shall not be held liable for any damage caused or sustained by any of the contestants, including any damage caused to third parties as a consequence of or during the implementation of the activities related to the contest.

9.2 Checks and audits

The contestants accept that, if they are awarded a prize, EFSA, OLAF and the Court of Auditors may carry out checks and audits in relation to the contest and the received prize.

9.3 Publicity

EFSA may use, for its communication and publicizing activities, information relating to the action, documents notably summaries for publication and public deliverables as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material that it receives from the winner of the prize, including in electronic form.

9.4 Processing of personal data

All personal data contained in the entry shall be processed in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L8 of 12.01.2001, p1) on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data by the Community institutions and bodies and on the free movement of such data. Such data shall be processed by the EFSA Controller solely in connection with the implementation and follow-up of the entry of the winner, without prejudice to a possible transmission to the bodies in charge of a monitoring or inspection task in accordance with European Community and European Union legislation.

Contestants may, on written request, gain access to their personal data and correct any information that is inaccurate or incomplete. They should address any questions regarding the processing of their personal data to the Controller, via the contact person announced in the rules of the contest. Please send in addition a scanned copy of your letter to the email address announced in the rules of the contest.

Contestants may, at any time, lodge a complaint against the processing of their personal data with the European Data Protection Supervisor.

EFSA will publish on its website the name of the prize winner/s, its locality, the prize amount and its nature and purpose. The contestant may request EFSA to waive such publication if disclosure risks threatening its security and safety or harm its commercial interest.

9.5 Applicable law and competent jurisdiction

The contest is governed by the applicable Union law complemented, where necessary, by the law of Italy. The General Court or, on appeal, the Court of Justice of the European Union, shall have sole jurisdiction to hear any dispute between the Union and any contestant concerning the interpretation, entry or validity of the rules of this contest, if such dispute cannot be settled amicably.

9.6 Financial penalties

Financial penalties and exclusion decisions may be imposed on participants under the situations in Article 106 of the EU Financial Regulation.

ANNEXES:

Annex 1: Register of Questions User Guide

Annex 2: DataSource, ForecastedVsActual, Forecasted2016perQuestionType,
QuestionStatusPerFSA,

Annex 3: EFSA Strategy

Annex 4: Draft Ownership Transfer Agreement

Annex 5: Admin Data Form (containing links to Bank Account and Legal Entity Forms)

Annex 6: Declaration on Honour on Exclusion Criteria